

Pedagogical Significance of Stages and Methods of Teaching Volleyball Training

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Abstract:

The article shows the stages, methods and means of teaching volleyball lessons through ways to achieve high efficiency.

Keywords: methodical teaching, professional skills, elementary teaching technology, technical training of a volleyball player, action-game skills, teaching process, vocational training, dictation, demonstration and explanatory methods.

INTRODUCTION.

As you know, the bright future of sports directly depends on the width and quality of the range of Sports Reserves. It directly depends on sports equipment, training bases, trainer skills, exercise training techniques and the art of training. Consequently, it is important to bring Uzbek sports to the world arena, raise it to a competitive level, organize children's Sports on a scientific basis and introduce effective pedagogical technologies in this regard. Only purposeful organizational and methodological activities are required to be carried out on a scientific basis. But, achieving such qualities can be done extremely carefully, at the cost of gradually increasing the training loads, in a "wavy" direction. Of course, this process is more efficient and intensive on the basis of continuous and regularity, as well as the tamoils of applying training loads in a way that suits the functional capabilities of the engaged "object". Since 2000, mass sports competitions such as multi-stage "sprouts of Hope", "harmonious generation", "Universiade", which have received the name of the small Olympics, have been held continuously in our country. Even so, in many places, sports clubs, sports schools, even in some national teams, the age, gender, physical and psychofunctional capabilities of children engaged in the organization of training on a scientific basis, planning downloads, selection of general and specialized exercises and their application are not carried out

based on the results of an objective test. Such shortcomings and problems are also prominent in the practice of training volleyball players.

MAIN PART.

The process of initial training in sports qualifications is considered the foundation of a multi-year system of sports training. The more thoroughly the initial training is based in terms of its organizational, methodological, scientific and material and technical point, the better the quality, the shorter and easier the path to training sports substitutes. But this, of course, will directly depend on the knowledge of the specialist, professional skills and qualifications. Therefore, one of the most attentive and basic sections of the curriculum designed to train professionals is the initial teaching methodology (technology).

One of the main conditions for achieving an effective result in the competition process is the technical training of the volleyball player, the level of improvement of his technical skills. So, the first and main goal of the teaching process is to master this game technique perfectly.

Movement-play qualifications – passing, receiving (defending) the ball, entering the ball into the game, striking, stumbling-are mastered, perfected, improved in the specified stages, using certain styles and tools. This process is carried out on the basis of pedagogical, biopsychological and biomechanical laws.

The teaching process is a pedagogical process that requires great skill, professional training from a coach-teacher. But even so, training in the technique of performing an action (game qualification) is also due to other significant reasons: the child's activity, the number, quality of training, duration of duration, auxiliary technical equipment, the conditions of the place of training, the child's interest, the "wealth" of movement, experience, etc.

It is also necessary to say that the duration of mastering the technique of movement also depends on the family conditions of the child, his social and economic capabilities and his mental state.

The above information and factors to consider in the training process should take place from planning documents based on a certain methodological procedure. In addition, it is necessary to determine the internal "secret" capabilities of the child, as well as the available factors, with the help of a selection program and exercises. The results obtained should serve as a supporting factor in the application of teaching methods, stages and technology.

The initial training process is carried out in several stages, and each of these stages includes its own style and tools.

General developmental exercises are applied to the player's physical perfection and bleaching of the movement skills and skills necessary for the player.

The special training of training, in which all exercises are combined in accordance with their direction, forms the main parts: general physical, special physical, technical, tactical, game training. Each type of preparation has its own leading factors with which the intended goal is achieved. At the same time, all types of preparations are inextricably linked with each other. For example, if the student is not physically well trained, he will not be able to do the striking technical exercise well in the attack. In this case, physical conditioning of the student is more useful than repeating the blow method many times.

The first stage is acquaintance with the technique of movement to be studied. In this case, methods of telling, showing and explaining are used. The teacher uses visual weapons along with the display in person: a motion picture, a picture film, a scheme, a field layout, etc.

The show should be accompanied by explanations. The first attempts of teachers form a primary sense of action in them.

The second stage is the study of the technique in a simplified (simplified) state. Success in this learning phase depends in many cases on the correct selection of approach exercises. They should be close to the technique of the movement being studied according to the shape of their structure and capable of being performed by students. A movement with a complex structure (attack shot), which is broken down into the main zvenos (pieces) that make it up. At this stage, such techniques as control are used (command, guidance, vision and hearing, visual progress, technical means, etc.), as well as visual movement (direct assistance from the teacher, the application of auxiliary equipment), information (Impact force on the ball, accuracy of falling, light or voice marking) will be of particular importance.

The third stage is to teach the technique in a complicated setting. The following are used in this: repetitive method, execution of movement in complex conditions, style of play and assessment, joint style, exercises "round circle". The repetition style is the most basic at this stage. It is only repeated many times that the qualification is formed. To generate qualification, repetition assumes the performance of exercises in different conditions (changing the conditions of movement, gradually complicating). Even when tired, the exercises are performed, the joint and playing styles will be aimed at simultaneously bleaching the technique, solving the issues of growing special physical qualities, and improving the technical and tactical training and playing skills.

The fourth stage-envisages strengthening the action in the game process. This uses the method of interpreting the actions performed (pictures, tables, educational films, pictorial films), techniques and tactics in the process of playing, special training tasks, methods of playing and "competition" (Table 1).

In preparatory and educational games, it is envisaged to study each method (qualification), improve and perfect it. The highest means of strengthening qualification is to compete.

Table 1. Stages, styles and tools for teaching volleyball training

Stages of training and the name of themnnng	Teaching methods	Teaching tools
Stage 1: To generate an understanding of the skills (effort) being taught	Explain-analyze, show-comment	Word, conversation, dialogue, discussion, pictures, templates, videos
Stage 2: Teaching qualifications in simple conditions (without additional tasks individually)	Piecemeal, element-and-phase training, skill-complete training, error correction, stimulation, return	Preparatory-approach referrer type imitation and basic technical exercises
Stage 3: Teaching skills in a complicated setting (giving situational tasks, in pairs, in the triad, etc.k.)	Teaching skills in full, with enhanced speed and accuracy, performing after different directions of action, reproductive return-based training, cross-analysis and assessment-based training.	All means in stages 1-2, general and special exercises are used at great speed and accuracy, exercises in pairs, triples, training and technical means
Stage 4: Continuing to teach, improve and perfect	All styles	All means and team matches

In teaching (teaching), active methods have great potential. Of particular importance among them- problem teaching (setting problem tasks) and the method of assessing its own appropriation. Setting problem tasks creates a situation, a situation in search of a solution, while self-assessment leads to

further activation of movement activity, which further increases the student's interest and teaches creative thinking.

It is no doubt that if training is carried out correctly following the stages, methods and means of training the above volleyball classes, qualified volleyball players will grow up in the future.

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